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EU WORK-LIFE INTEGRATION: LEGISLATIVE DEVELOPMENTS

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to analyze the evolution of work-life balance legislation in the European Union (EU), from its adoption in 2019 to its mandatory implementation among member states in 2022 or later, prompted by EU infringement procedures. Our research begins with an overview of first steps taken towards such policies since 2017, elucidating the concepts and significance of work-life balance in contemporary society, and briefly discussing the historical context of relevant laws and acts that paved the way for the most recent one, Directive EU 2019/1158. Additionally, we will outline the key provisions of the work-life balance directive and highlight primary studies that have monitored its implementation across EU member states (such as Coface, Deloitte, European Commission, etc.). Our paper will be added to literature which contributes to a better understanding of work-life balance legislation of the European Union also by updating about its implementation in all EU 27 member states.

Keywords: work-life balance concepts, work-life balance legislation, European Union, human rights

Jel classification: I30, I31, J08, J22, J28

1. Introduction

The proposal for such a directive originated in 2017 (COM/2017/0253) and encompassed several key aspects. These included the introduction of paternity leave, providing a minimum of 10 working days around the time of a child's birth. Additionally, the proposal introduced carers' leave, granting workers who offer personal care or support to a relative or cohabitant 5 days of leave per year. Another significant element was the extension of the existing right to request flexible working arrangements—such as reduced working hours, adaptable schedules, and changes in the place of work—to encompass all working parents of children up to at least 8 years old, as well as all caregivers (Eurostat, 2020).

The Directive on Work-Life Balance for Parents and Caregivers (Directive EU 2019/1158) was finally adopted in the EU after two years, in June/2019 and all EU member states were required to implement it into their own legislation by August 2022. In 2027 Member States have to communicate to the Commission the stage of the Directive implementation necessary in drawing up a report.

2. European Union - Historical development of work-life balance policies in the EU

The EU's commitment to work-life balance extends far beyond the adoption of the Directive on Work-Life Balance for Parents and Careers in 2019, as it has consistently sought to improve working conditions and prioritize the welfare of its citizens throughout its history.

Since the 1970's and 1980's, were adopted the first European directives regarding the protection of workers' health and safety, which had a direct impact on the working environment and hours worked. In 1978, the Council of the European Union passed a resolution on the first *Action Programme on Safety and Health at Work in the EU*. The Council emphasized the need to monitor workers' health and also considered psychosocial factors, suggesting that adapting work to workers would promote their physical and mental well-being (Castillo, 2016). The Council Directive with improvements in the safety and health of workers at work (89/391/EEC), came into force in 1989 and was fully implemented across all EU member states by 1992.

In the 1990's, was adopted a directive concerning maternity leave, parental leave, and the rights of workers with children, in an attempt to support families and to promote a work-life

balance (92/85/EEC). The research paper entitled: *"Maternity and paternity leave in the EU"* published by the European Parliamentary Research Service (EPRS,2022) defines the terms that such directives and/or legislations often used (i) maternity leave which is a leave granted to mothers during the period before and after childbirth; (ii) paternity leave, which is given to fathers or recognized second parents, similar to maternity leave and (iii) parental leave is available to either parent after the maternity or paternity leave period.

According to their research paper, maternity rights were set out in the 1992 through Pregnant Workers Directive (92/85/EEC) which comprises measures for improvements in the safety and health at work for pregnant workers and/or for workers who have recently given birth or are breastfeeding. Dir. 92/85/EEC has been changed in current consolidated version on June 2019. In present the final form of this EU legislation sets the minimum period for maternity leave at 14 weeks, with 2 weeks compulsory leave before and/or after confinement and an adequate allowance subject to national legislation (EPRS,2022).

In the 2000's, the EU have also implemented some directives with a focus on gender equality, working conditions and in achievements of a balance between the professional and personal lives of employees. Among them we mention: Dir.2003/88/EC; Dir.2006/54/EC; Dir. 2010/41/EU and Dir.2010/18/EU.

Directive 2003/88/EC, known also as the Working Time Directive, established main guidelines for working hours, rest periods, annual leave, and maximum weekly working time for workers and particularly of those involved in shift and night work. According to this directive, each worker (from public or private sectors) was entitled with a minimum daily rest period of 11 consecutive hours in a 24-hour period, and a minimum uninterrupted rest period of 24 hours at every seven-day period (in addition to the 11 hours' daily rest if possible).

Some other issues of Directive 2003/88/EC were referring to: a rest break for those workers with a working day longer than six hours; an average weekly working time limit at 48 hours and at least four weeks of paid annual leave. Regarding the night workers, member states were required to establish the working hours not more than an average of 8(eight) hours in any 24-hour period. Both night workers and shift workers would receive safety and health protection comparable to other workers" (OSHA,2023).

Directive 2006/54/CE of the EU Parliament and Council (July, 2006), known as *"Directive on equal treatment between women and men in matters of employment and occupation"*, was adopted in order to achieve equal opportunities and treatment for men and women in their workplaces, to eliminate discrimination in employment and to ensure equal chances for women and men to be hired and/or to advance in their career. The directive's objectives was to equalize payment for similar work, ensuring fair opportunities for advancement at work, facilitating access to training and professional development, and creating a safe environment by preventing harassment and violence in the workplace. the work. This directive was a significant step in the EU fight for gender equality, in women's rights promotions and in gender discrimination reduction in the workforce across the European Union member countries.

Directive 2010/41/UE, issued by the European Parliament and Council on 7th, July 2010, focuses on ensuring equal treatment between men and women who are self-employed or contribute to such activities. In the realm of self-employed work, this means no gender-based discrimination should occur when starting, expanding, or equipping a business. Moreover, the directive 2010/41/UE (art.17), recognizes the role of spouses/partners in family businesses, granting them access to social protection rights.

Directive 2010/18/EU of the Council on 8th March 2010, actually implemented a revised framework agreement on parental leave, concluded one year earlier (18th June 2009) by the European inter professional organizations of social partners (BUSINESSEUROPE, UEAPME, CEEP, and CES). The purpose of parental leave was to facilitate the professional and family responsibilities and promote treatment equality between men and women. According to this

directive, parental leave was granted for a minimum of four months on non-transferred base. Moreover, Member States and/or social partners were responsible for protecting workers against unfavorable treatment or dismissal based on the request or exercise of parental leave. Additionally, the directive allowed workers to be absent from work in cases of force majeure, such as family emergencies, illness, or accidents requiring their immediate presence (Directive 2010/18/EU, Clause 7). Directive 2010/18/EU was repealed with the introduction of Directive EU 2019/1158, mentioned in the current paper's introduction.

Finally, the last and newest one, the Directive EU 2019/1158 represents a continuation of the EU's efforts in maintaining and expanding the rights of workers (and their families) regarding work-life balance.

The three main rights provided by the Directive according to COFACE Families Europe (2022) were: paternity leave, parental leave and carers' leave. In more detailed picture the directive improvements were: (i) 10 working days of paternity leave for fathers or equivalent second parents (art. 4) remunerated at least at the level of sick pay (art. 8, rec.30) compared to previous law (2010/18/EU) which had not legal provisions for paternity leave, (ii) at least four months of parental leave per parent, of which 2 (two) months that cannot be transferred between parents (art.5), compared to previous law from 2010, which had just 1(one) month non-transferable between parents, remunerated at adequate level by Member States (art. 8, rec. 31); (iii) at least five working days of leave per year, with additional flexibility on how to allocate them (art. 6) for caregivers with no mentions about remuneration at EU level, (rec.32), compared to previous law (2010/18/EU) which had not legal provisions for caregivers leave; (iv) the right to request flexible working arrangements (flexible work schedules, reduced working hours). Article 9 states that Member States shall take the necessary measures to ensure that workers with children up to at least eight years, and carers, have the right to request flexible working arrangements for caring purposes (COFACE Families Europe, 2022).

3.Implementation of work-life directive in EU member countries

On June 13, 2019, the Council approved the Directive with a notable majority. A few countries Denmark, Hungary, the Netherlands, and Slovenia voted against, while Austria and Poland abstained (EWL, 2019). After its adoption in 2019, the Directive's text was published in the Official Journal of the EU in all languages. Member States were granted a period until August 2, 2022 (a span of three years) to integrate the necessary laws, regulations, and administrative measures to align with the directive into their national legislations. However, on September 21, 2022, the Commission took action against 19 Member States for not communicating their transposition measures. Further analysis of countries replies revealed that 11 of these countries had not fully implemented the Directive. As a result, the Commission was started an infringement procedure to 11 Member States: Belgium, Czechia, Ireland, Greece, Spain, France, Croatia, Cyprus, Luxembourg, Austria, and Slovenia. At that time, these countries were granted an additional two months to address the issues or face potential referral to the European Union's Court of Justice.

Several studies aimed at tracking the implementation stage of EU Directive 2019/1158 on work-life balance in EU member states. We will mention the most extensive studies carried out in this direction and we will detail the most recent ones.

A first study we mention is one of Coface Families Europe report about assessment of the EU Work-Life Balance 2019 Directive transposition, named: *“EU Work-life Balance Directive transposition in action: A mixed picture”* (Coface, 2022). This report presents clear and detailed the findings in matter of Directive implementation for 10 of the EU member states: Belgium, Croatia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Poland and Spain (a comparative analysis of the Directive EU 2019/1158 transposition). We here present briefly their findings about implementation of each directive's item separately for those 10 EU countries (paternity leave, parental leave, carers leave, flexible working arrangements before and during Covid19).

a) As for paternity leave, according to COFACE, paternity leave has been fully transposed in 8 of these countries, but in two countries, the minimum of 10 days paternity was not transposed for the 2nd of August 2022 deadline. A delay in implementation of paternity leave was recorded in Hungary and Germany.

b) While all Member States comply with the minimum four-month parental leave duration set by the Directive (Coface, 2022), full transposition of the two months of non-transferability is lacking across countries. Certain countries (such as France, Belgium, Italy, Spain) don't adequately pay parental leave, a situation incongruent with Article 8(3) promoting balanced parental leave uptake. Eligibility criteria generally cover self-employed workers, adhering to the Directive's service length requirement of up to a year. Most member states offer options for part-time, short-time, and fragmented parental leave. The window for utilizing parental leave ranges from 2-3 years (Finland, Lithuania, France, Spain) to 12 years (Belgium, Italy). COFACE Families Europe advocates for extending parental leave to encompass each child's first 12 years.

c) Carers' leave is integrated into the legal frameworks of many of the 10 Member States studied by Coface (2022), although variations in transposition exist. In some countries, the regulations fall below the norms set out by the Directive (e.g., Poland, Spain, Finland, Croatia). Also, some countries have age-specific or limited paid carer leave schemes in some cases, limited to caring for children up to the age of 18. This contrasts with the Directive's more encompassing definition of carers' leave as *"leave from work for workers in order to provide personal care or support to a relative, or to a person who lives in the same household as the worker, and who is in need of significant care or support for a serious medical reason, as defined by each Member State"* (Directive EU 2019/1158, art 3). Carers' leave often remains unpaid or is low paid in several Member States (e.g., Belgium, Germany, Spain), although allowances might be stipulated during the care period. Furthermore, there are cases where certain participant Member States fall below the 5 working days specified in the Directive (Poland, Spain) and some cases where countries plan to exceed these minimum standards (Germany).

A more recent study conducted by Deloitte in 2023 (Deloitte,2023) focuses on the implementation of two EC directives across some other 10(ten) EU member countries: Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, and Slovenia. Four of these countries are also mentioned in the Coface study (Croatia, Hungary Lithuania and Poland) providing us with a more current development. Based on their April 2023 study, it's confirmed that 9 out of the 10 EU countries analyzed (excluding the Czech Republic) have successfully implemented the provisions of EU Directive 2019/1158 concerning Work-Life Balance.

4. Conclusions

In the European Union, work-life balance improved significantly as a result of the Work-Life Balance Directive's adoption (EU/2019/1158). The directive derives from the need for employees (especially parents and carers) to strike a balance between their professional and personal responsibilities. Its evolution derived from a good understanding of the fact that workers are not only productive contributors to the economy, but also have private lives, caring for children or other members of their families.

Analysis of the historical context of work-life balance policies demonstrated that these were not isolated efforts, but rather part of a complex one, made by all EU countries in order to prioritize the development of its citizens lives.

The Work-Life Balance Directive (EU/2019/1158) mainly focuses on paternity leave, parental leave, and carers' leave, aiming to comprehensively promote a more supportive work environment. The inclusion of a 10-day paternity leave for fathers or equivalent second parents (Article 4), complemented by a remuneration framework set at a minimum sick pay level (Article

8, recommendation 30), marks a noteworthy departure from the absence of paternity leave provisions in the previous law (2010/18/EU).

Furthermore, the directive ensures that each parent is entitled to at least four months of parental leave, with two months being exclusively non-transferable between parents (Article 5). Compared to the previous law of 2010 (2010/18/EU), through this extension of parental leave, (EU/2019/1158) now is recognized legally the significance of family time providing a foundation for a healthier work-life balance.

The requirement for remuneration at a suitable level, determined by Member States (Article 8, recommendation 31), adds a critical dimension to ensuring the feasibility of such leaves. Additionally, the directive introduces a minimum of five working days of leave per year for caregivers, coupled with enhanced flexibility in leave allocation (Article 6). Although specific remuneration details are absent at the EU level (Recommendation 32), this provision marks a significant leap from the previous law (2010/18/EU), which lacked legal provisions for caregiver leave.

The directive also refers to the right to request flexible working arrangements, such as more flexible working hours and/or a reduced working schedule underlining how the nature of work is constantly changing. Article 9 emphasizes that Member States should have a duty to establish measures to give workers with children up to eight years of age, as well as carers, the ability to seek flexible working arrangements (COFACE Families Europe, 2022).

There is a mixed picture of progress and challenges regarding member states implementation of work-life directive. Austria already has legislation in place that provides conditions equivalent to, or more generous than, those in the EU Directive 2019/1158, some other countries have faced obstacles and complexities in incorporating them into their national legislation.

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